

Formulation and Evaluation of Omeprazole Floating Tablet for The Treatment of Peptic Ulcer

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ABSTRACT

Peptic ulcers, Zollinger-Ellison syndrome, and acid-related gastrointestinal illnesses including Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease (GERD) can all be effectively treated with omeprazole, a popular proton pump inhibitor (PPI). Omeprazole's traditional formulation, however, has drawbacks including low bioavailability and quick stomach emptying, which lowers its therapeutic effectiveness. The creation of omeprazole floating tablets has shown promise as a solution to these issues. By providing extended gastric retention and improving drug release at the site of action, these tablets are made to float in the stomach fluid. Omeprazole's controlled, prolonged release from floating tablets improves bioavailability and prolongs therapeutic activity, which may lower dosage frequency and increase patient compliance. Important excipients are utilized to support the floating mechanism and preserve the stability of the medication, such as sodium bicarbonate, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), or other polymers. By minimizing variations in the drug's plasma levels and improving the management of acid-related disorders, this novel dosage form seeks to maximize the pharmacokinetic profile of omeprazole. The current study explores the potential of omeprazole floating tablets to improve the clinical results of acid reflux and other gastrointestinal illnesses by examining their formulation, characterization, and in vitro assessment.

Keywords: Floating tablet, Omeprazole (API), Floating drug delivery system, HPMC K 4 M, HPMC K15 M

INTRODUCTION

A floating tablet represents a form of gastroretentive drug delivery system (GRDDS) engineered to stay afloat within the gastric environment for prolonged periods. This extended buoyancy facilitates sustained drug release and enhances gastric retention time. The tablet achieves floatation either through the incorporation of low-density polymers or by utilizing gas-generating agents that react upon contact with gastric fluids, ensuring that the dosage form remains suspended in the stomach.¹ Omeprazole, a proton pump inhibitor that stops the stomach from creating gastric acid, is often taken as a regular tablet at a dose of 15 mg. Omeprazole has a low water solubility and is chemically labile in an acid environment. Omeprazole has a biological half-life of 1 to 1.2 hours.²

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Omeprazole and Microcrystalline cellulose PH 102 was obtained as gift sample from Murli Krishna Pharma Pvt. Lit. Ranjangoan, HPMC K 4 M, HPMC K 15 M, PVP K 30, was obtained from Sharadchandra Pawar College of Pharmacy Dumbarwadi, Otur, Pune, Maharashtra, India- 412409. Sodium Bicarbonate, Citric Acid, Magnesium stearate, Talc was obtained from Delight College of Pharmacy, Koregaon Bhima, Pune, Maharashtra, India- 412216.

Preparation of Omeprazole Tablet

Step 1: Solution Preparation

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Dissolved Required Quantity of PVP K30 and Omeprazole API completely in water to make a clear solution by using mechanical stirrer.

Step 2: Dry Mixing

Sodium bicarbonate, Citric acid, Magnesium stearate, Talc, MCC PH 102 (Microcrystalline Cellulose), HPMC K4M, HPMC K15M are pass through the mesh no.24 and mix in the bowl for dry mixing purpose.

Step 3: Preparation of Drug and Excipient Damp Mass

Drug solution which is directly added into the Dry mixture in Rapid mixture Granulator and prepare damp mass by using required quantity of purified water. Mix well until a damp mass is formed (the mixture should hold together when pressed but should not be too wet).

Step 4: Wet Sieving

Pass the damp mass through sieve no. #24 to form uniform granules.

Step 5: Drying

Dry the wet granules properly in Tray Dryer to remove moisture content from Drug granules

Step 6: Compression

Compress the dried granules into tablets using a single tablet compression machine.

Step 7: Coating

Coat the compressed tablets by using film coating solution (HPMC and Isopropyl Alcohol) to achieve uniform layer of tablet.

Figure 1: Omeprazole Floating Tablet

Table 1: Formulation of Omeprazole Tablet

Ingredients	Batch A	Batch B	Batch C	Batch D	Batch E	Batch F
Omeprazole	30	30	30	30	30	30
HPMC K 4 M	90	90	-	-	45	45
HPMC K 15 M	-	-	90	90	45	45
Sod. Bicarbonate	10	20	10	20	10	20
Citric Acid	20	10	20	10	20	10
PVP K30M	20	20	20	20	20	20
Mg. stearate	02	02	02	02	02	02
Talc	02	02	02	02	02	02
MCC PH 102	30	30	30	30	30	30

Preformulation studies:

1. Physical appearance:

Omeprazole was analysed for colour, odour and texture. The data is ported in table 2.

2. Meiting point determination:

The melting point of the drug was determined using the capillary fusion method. A small quantity of the drug was packed and sealed in a glass capillary tube, which was then placed in an inverted position within the melting point apparatus. The temperature at which the drug melted was recorded and compared with its reported literature value. The results are presented in Table 2.³

3. Solubility Analysis:

The solubility of the drug was assessed by placing a small quantity of the sample in separate test tubes containing various solvents including distilled water, ethanol, and methanol. The extent of dissolution was visually examined to determine the drug's solubility profile. This test helps evaluate the drug's affinity for different solvents, providing essential insights for formulation development and dosage form design.⁴

Table 2: Parameters and Observation of omeprazole

Sr. No.	Parameter	Observation
1	Colour	White
2	Odour	Slightly characteristic odour
3	Texture	Powder
4	Melting point	151- 155 ⁰ C
5	Solubility	Freely soluble in methanol

4. Determination of Absorbance Maxima:

Omeprazole was quantitatively analysed using a UV spectrophotometer with methanol solution. A standard calibration curve was established by preparing a stock solution with a concentration of 1000µg/mL in methanol. Test solutions were then

prepared by diluting the sample to concentration of 2,4,6,8 and 10 µg/mL and their absorbance was measured at the max of 301 nm. The plot of absorbance v/s concentration (µg/mL) was plotted and data was subjected to weighed linear regression analysis in Microsoft excel.⁵

Table 3: Calibration curve of Omeprazole

Concentration (mg\ ml)	Absorbance (AU)
0	0.000
2	0.192
4	0.384
6	0.576
8	0.768
10	0.960

Figure 2: Calibration Curve of Omeprazole

EVALUATION OF OMEPRAZOLE TABLET

1. Pre-compression Parameter

i. Angle of repose

A powder is allowed to pass through a funnel and land freely on a surface to calculate the angle of repose. When the pile comes into contact with the funnel's tip, further powder is not added. Without upsetting the pile, a circle is drawn around it. Table 4 displays the measurements for the height and diameter of the resultant cone. After three iterations of the same process, the average value is calculated. This formula is used to determine the angle of repose.⁶

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} h/r$$

Where, θ = Angle of repose,

h = height of the powder cone,

r = radius of the powder.

ii. Bulk Density:

Disassemble any agglomerates that could have developed during storage and add around 100g of the test sample (M), weighed with an accuracy of 0.1%, to a dry 250 ml cylinder without compacting. Technique II, Choose a sample mass with a 150–250 ml untapped apparent volume. For apparent quantities between 50 and 100 ml, a 100 ml cylinder is utilized. Carefully fill the cylinder. If required, carefully level the powder without compacting it. Then, as indicated in Table 4, read the unsettled apparent volume (V_o).

Utilizing the following formula, get the bulk density in g/ml:⁷

$$\text{Bulk density (BD)} = M/V_b$$

Where, BD = Bulk Density,

M = Mass of the powder,

V_b = Bulk Volume of the powder.

iii. Tapped Density:

A measuring cylinder was filled with a precisely weighed 1.25gm of powder. Using an appropriate mechanically tapped density tester, mechanically tap the sample-containing cylinder by elevating it and letting it fall under its own weight at a notional rate of 300 drops per minute. Measure the tapped volume (V_a) after 500 taps of the cylinder. Measure the tapped volume as (V_b) after repeating the process for 750 more tapping sands. as seen in Table 4. Repeating the tapings 1,250 times was necessary since the difference between V_a and V_b was greater. The tapped density was then determined using formula⁸

$$\text{Tapped density (TD)} = M/V_t$$

Where, TD = Tapped Density,

M = Mass of the powder,

V_t = Tapped volume.

iv. Carr's index:

As seen in Table 4, the compressibility index of granules may be calculated using Carr's index, which was calculated using the following formula:⁹

Carr's index (%) = (Tapped density – Bulk density) / Tapped density * 100.

v. Hausner Ratio:

Hausner ratio (HR) is used to predict the flow of the powders. It is computed by the following equation:

$$HR = P_t/P_b$$

where, P_t = tapped density,

P_b = bulk density.

Hausner ratio less than 1.25 is a good indicator of flow properties.

Post compression parameters:

Figure 3: Hardness tester

I. Friability and hardness:

A Monsanto Hardness Tester was used to measure the tablet's hardness. From each batch, ten tablets were chosen at random and their hardness was examined. Additionally, the mean and standard deviation were computed. Roche Friabilator conducted the friability test. By using a plastic container that rotates at 25 rpm and drops the tablets six inches apart with each rotation, ten weighted tablets were exposed to the combined effects of attrition and shock. The tablets were de-dusted and reweighed every 100 rotations. Table 5 illustrates the calculation of the % friability.¹⁰

Figure 4: Fraibility tester

II. Weight variation:

Ten 200 mg tablets were chosen at random from each batch, and each tablet's weight was measured separately before the average was determined and compared to the individual tablet weight. As seen in Table 5, the % weight difference was computed from this and subsequently verified for USP requirements.¹¹

III. In vitro buoyancy studies

The floating lag time was used to calculate the in vitro buoyancy. A 250 ml beaker with 200 ml of 0.1 N HCl was filled with the tablets. Floating Lag Time (FLT) is the amount of time needed for the tablet to rise to the surface and float, and Total Floating Time (TFT) is the amount of time the tablet stayed buoyant, as indicated in Table 6.

IV. In Vitro Dissolution Study¹²

The USP type I dissolving equipment was used to conduct an in vitro drug release evaluation of floating tablets. To stop the tablet from escaping to the release medium, a piece of muslin fabric was placed over the baskets. In the dissolving investigation, a tablet containing 10 mg of Omeprazole was utilized. The test was conducted in 0.1N HCl (900 ml) with stirring at 50 rpm and maintained at 37±0.5°C. At regular intervals, 10 ml of the sample was taken out, and the same volume of brand-new dissolving liquid was added to the dissolution vessel. The absorbance of the gathered aliquots was measured spectrophotometrically at 300 nm, respectively. Calculations were made using calibration curves created in the corresponding media concentrations. The correction factor was used in accordance with the equation below to account for the loss of medication in the aliquot substituted.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation parameters:

The main factor for determining the material's suitability for the formulation was its precompression characteristics. When choosing any material for dosage form formulation, it was crucial to know the bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's

ratio, and angle of repose because the goal was to use the direct compression method for tablet formulation. The assessed characteristics of bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, and angle of repose for different tablet formulations are shown in Table 4. The evaluation parameters' results indicate that it is appropriate to use as the preferred formulation material.

Table 4. Evaluation of preformulation parameters

Code	Bulk density	Tapped density	Carr's index	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose
Batch A	2.05	2.97	30.97	1.45	24.76
Batch B	2.20	2.76	20.29	1.25	28.64
Batch C	2.18	2.37	19.70	0.84	25.09
Batch D	2.54	2.44	8.02	1.09	29.81
Batch E	2.03	2.75	26.18	1.35	27.84
Batch F	2.80	3.00	6.67	1.07	30.01

Post compression parameter:

All formulations of tablets maintained a smooth, flat-faced circular shape that is off-white in color. The tablets' hardness was assessed using a Monsanto tester, yielding values ranging from 4.3 to 4.6 kg/cm². Using a friabilator, friability was assessed and determined to be 0.38 to 0.52. This suggests that the

tablets have a satisfactory level of mechanical resistance. The estimations of drug content yielded values between 90.56% to 96.33%, indicating a high degree of uniformity in drug content across various formulations. The % weight variation of all the tablets was within the Pharmacopoeial limits, so they all passed the weight variation test. The outcomes are displayed in Table 5.

Table 5: Evaluation of Post Compression Parameters

SR\NO.	Hardness test(kg\cm ²)	Friability (%)	Weight variation	Drug content (%)
Batch A	4.6	0.47	0.49	91.40%
Batch B	4.5	0.52	0.51	90.56%
Batch C	4.4	0.48	0.47	96.00%
Batch D	4.5	0.44	0.48	93.13%
Batch E	4.4	0.38	0.50	92.34%
Batch F	4.3	0.34	0.49	96.33%

Table 6 displays the buoyancy lag time and floating duration measured using a 100 ml beaker filled with 0.1N HCl medium. Based on the findings, it can be

said that the batch contains only HPMC K4M and HPMC K15M demonstrated good performance. The total floating time is 12 hours, with a buoyancy lag time of 60 to 84 seconds.

Table 6: Batch Buoyancy Lag Total Floating

Batch	Time(sec)	Time(hrs)
A	81	>10
B	78	>10
C	68	>12
D	84	>10
E	62	>12
F	60	>12

The USP dissolving equipment 2 (paddle) was used to conduct dissolution investigations on the floating formulations F1 through F6 in 900 milliliters of 0.1N HCl medium. The bubbling floating tablet of as indicated in Table 7, omeprazole was prepared in 6 distinct batches, A through F, utilizing the hydrophilic polymers HPMC K 4 M and HPMC K 15 M in addition to the effervescent agents sodium

bicarbonate and citric acid. 30% of the drug was released in the first two hours, and 94% of the drug was released in the next seven hours, respectively (table 7). The release rate was raised in the following order among these formulas: F > A > B > C > E > D. In 7 hours, 94% of the medication was discharged. Therefore, it may be said that Omeprazole's effervescent floating tablet provided a gradual and thorough drug release distributed over 7 hours.

Table 7: Cumulative % drug released of A to F (0.1N HCl) Formulation

Batch	1hr	2hr	3hr	4hr	5hr	6hr	7hr
A	18.04	24.08	39.15	49.20	62.26	87.09	92.17
B	24.14	29.06	36.28	49.27	66.18	84.01	91.05
C	16.00	26.11	44.22	56.09	62.13	73.18	89.20
D	22.10	38.20	44.16	63.14	67.29	77.20	84.05
E	24.19	31.02	42.07	59.25	64.19	81.14	86.22
F	20.09	32.21	54.12	59.17	63.03	74.10	95.15

Figure 5: In vitro drug release

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated floating tablets of omeprazole designed to enhance gastric retention and improve the therapeutic efficacy in the management of peptic ulcers and other acid-related gastrointestinal disorders. Pre-compression parameters confirmed the excellent flow properties of the granules, while post-compression evaluations demonstrated that all formulations exhibited acceptable hardness, friability, weight variation, and drug content uniformity within pharmacopoeial limits. The floating ability tests indicated prolonged buoyancy with floating times

exceeding 12 hours for selected batches, particularly formulations containing a combination of HPMC K4M and HPMC K15M. In vitro drug release studies revealed a sustained release profile, with Batch F achieving approximately 95% drug release over 7 hours. These results suggest that the developed floating tablet system not only provides controlled and extended drug release but also holds promise in improving bioavailability, reducing dosing frequency, and enhancing patient compliance. Future in vivo studies are warranted to confirm the clinical efficacy and pharmacokinetic advantages of the optimized formulation.

REFERENCE

1. Agale KA, Shinde SP, A Review on Floating Tablet, *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics* 2025;15(2):204-209. DOI: <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-9817-3697>
2. Patel D, Patel N, Shah S, Patel M, Formulation and evaluation of enteric coated tablet of proton pump inhibitor, *Int J Pharm Res Bio-Sci*, 2012;1(3):122-138.
3. Singh A, Verma R, Melting Point Determination of Pharmaceutical Compounds Using Capillary Fusion Method, *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics* 2025;15(2):221–224. DOI: <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-9817-3697>
4. Patel RJ, Mehta SK, Solubility Profiling of Pharmaceutical Compounds in Common Solvents for Preformulation Studies, *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics* 2025;15(2):216–220. DOI: <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-9817-3697>
5. Sharma A, Patel H, UV Spectrophotometric Quantification of Omeprazole Using Methanol, Calibration Curve and Data Analysis Using Microsoft Excel, *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics* 2025;15(2):210-215. DOI: <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-9817-3697>
6. Goole J, Vanderbist F, Amighi K, Development and evaluation of new multiple-unit levodopa sustained-release floating dosage forms, *International journal of pharmaceutics*, 2007;334(1-2):35-41. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2006.10.018>
7. Sharma S, Pawar A, Low density multiparticulate system for pulsatile release of meloxicam, *International journal of pharmaceutics*, 2006;313(1-2):150-158. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2006.02.001>
8. Rouge N, Allémann E, Gex-Fabry M, Balant L, et al., Comparative pharmacokinetic study of a floating multiple-unit capsule, a high-density multiple-unit capsule and an immediate-release tablet containing 25 mg atenolol, *Pharmaceutica Acta Helveticae*, 1998;73(2):81-87. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-6865\(97\)00050-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-6865(97)00050-2)
9. Santus G, Lazzarini C, Bottoni G, Sandefer EP, et al., An in vitro-in vivo investigation of oral bioadhesive controlled release furosemide formulations, *European journal of pharmaceutics and biopharmaceutics*, 1997;44(1):39-52. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0939-6411\(97\)00100-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0939-6411(97)00100-8)
10. Klaus EA, Lavy E, Friedman M, Hoffman A, Expandable gastroretentive dosage forms, *Journal of controlled release*, 2003;90(2):143-162. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-3659\(03\)00203-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-3659(03)00203-7)
11. Deshpande AA, Shah NH, Rhodes CT, Malick W, Development of a novel controlled-release system for gastric retention, *Pharmaceutical research*, 1997;14:815-819.
12. Park K, Enzyme-digestible swelling hydrogels as platforms for long-term oral drug delivery: synthesis and characterization, *Biomaterials*, 1988;9(5):435-441. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0142-9612\(88\)90009-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0142-9612(88)90009-9)

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